

WISDOM: BECOMING KNOWLEDGEABLE

Dr. Surendra Pal Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Teacher Education, D.S. College, Aligarh

Abstract

The present article aims to study the information processing theory in relation to Learning, memory and intelligence. It also try to find out the continuum of alignment of all theories in relation to improve knowledge and become knowledgeable. The paper present a assumed framework of various aspects of learning, memory and intelligence with special reference to 'Wisdom'. One another attempt to present a joint effort of Philosophy and Psychology. Article mostly based on the original thoughts which will be helpful to initiate a new dimension of cognitive activities.

Key words : Central Executive, Self Regulatory Memory, Meta-cognition Wisdom and Consciousness.

Learning is a process through which experience and training courses permanent change in knowledge and behaviour. The change may be deliberative or unintentional, better or worse, correct or incorrect, conscious and unconscious (Mayer 2011, Schunk 2012). Learning changes occurs through experience and training (interaction with environment) not caused by maturation and disease. There are the two view of study about learning and learning theories. Behavioural view of learning and cognitive view of learning.

Behavioural learning theories explains learning as a change in behaviour and it emphasized the effect of external events. This approach of learning supported by J.B. Watson. Behavioural theories explains learning as a process of association between stimulus and response. In this approach, human being considered as a machine in a mentalism way.

Cognitive view of learning explains learning is extended and transforming, and understanding process we already have as a matter of memory. Cognitive view of learning is a general approach that view learning as an active mental process of acquiring remembering and using knowledge. According to the cognitive view people actively choose, practice, pay attention, ignore, reflect, and make many decisions as their purpose.

The cognitive and Behavioural view of learning differ in their assumption about the process of learning. According to cognitive view knowledge and strategies are learned, and then knowledge and strategies change behaviour. On the other hand, behaviour view of learning assumed that new behaviour's themselves are learned.

Knowledge is the product of learning but learning is the more then the end product of previous learning, it also guide new learning. Cognitive approach suggest that one of the most important element in learning process is what the individual brings to new learning situation. What we already know is the foundation and frame for constructing all future learning. Cognitive approach include both subject-specific understanding and to have the knowledge of something is to remember it over time and

sketch pad holds visual and spatial information and episodic buffer integrate information from phonological loop, visuo-spatial sketch pad and long term memory.

Sources: Baddley, 2007; Baddeley, Hitch & Allen, 2009; Jarrold Tam, Baddeley & Hancey, 2011

This model of working memory explain the information processing of immediate consciousness (cognition) in terms of the memory. The role of central executive is most important to select the information for attention and comprehension. It works just like a monitor of the information which are under process at a point of time. It determines the context of cognition. When a person received too much information and some time complexity of thoughts in mind both leads cognitive load. Cognitive load is the volume of resources necessary to complete a task. The resources required by the task (intrinsic), the resources required by the process stimuli irrelevant to the task (Extrinsic) and deep process of information related to the task including the application of prior knowledge to a new task (Germane).

Information Processing in long term memory is a product which takes place apart from the cognition. Long term memory is a content of sub-cognition processes. But when we involve in the information processing at LTM level the information automatically comes under the process of cognition and under central executive activation. Thus the information, acknowledge, understand and use for the cognitive adaptation. Central executive, phonological loop and visuo-spatial sketch pad work on the immediate cognition level in STM. Similarly, the Self Regulatory Knowledge, Declaration Knowledge and Procedural Knowledge work on sub-cognition level of processing. It is very important to keep these processing in continuum of alignment in between Self Regulatory and Central Executive. Declarative Knowledge verbal information, facts, knowing that something in the case. Procedural Knowledge demonstrate when we perform a task knowing how and self regulatory knowledge manage your learning or knowing how and when to use your declarative and procedural knowledge.

How to Become Knowledgeable

Theoretical explanation of information processing approach claims on some principles (Strategies) to improve our knowledge and memory and how to make best use

of information stored in our mind for the development of declarative memory and make it meaningful. We use memories procedures which improve the remembering and make skilled in the art of storage, and retrieval of information. Memories techniques include the method of loci (place), Acronames, chunking, key word method, rote memorization. As far as concern with the procedural memory boosting we can use automated basic skills based on association and autonomous and domain. Specific strategies consciously applied skill to reach goal in a particular subject or problem. The above memory boosting devices works on the basis of partial improvement in the knowledge, it improves the retrieval of the facts which are stored in our memory. One another important issues to consider for understand that these all techniques related to cognitive domain so that emotional and behavioural aspects could not be nourished. So it leads to make our students and adults as computer / machine.

So what should be a an approach to become knowledgeable? Memory improvement is a partial development therefore we have to focus on the holistic approach which develop cognitive affective and psycho-motor aspect of human personality. Human being a super-conscious and intellectual organism so we should try to develop 'Wisdom' through the metacognitive monitoring. It fulfills the aim of all round development of human being.

Meta-cognition term was first defined by John H. Flavell (1979). Meta-cognition can be define as thinking above thinking. It is a mental ability which monitor all mental activities and regulate them. Michelle Reconscente (2008) said, "Knowledge or awareness of self as a knower." Meta cognition literally means higher-order knowledge about the own thinking as well as ability to use this knowledge to manage your own cognitive process meta-cognition involves three kinds of the knowledge.

1. Declarative knowledge – It is about yourself as a learner, the abilities skills and memory that influence the learning.
2. Procedural knowledge – Knowledge about how to use strategies.
3. Self Regulatory knowledge – Knowing the conditions about the task to fulfill the Aims.

Shunk (2012) Meta-cognition is the strategic application of declarative, procedural and self regulatory knowledge to accomplish goal and solve problems. As the executive entity of the cognitive functions Meta-cognitive regular thinking and learning. The three essential skills used by Meta-cognitions – (i) Planning about time, ability, skills and resources. (ii) Monitoring is a real time awareness of 'How I am doing', have I prepare and plan well. (iii) Evaluating involve making judgement about the process an outcome. In breif Meta-cognition makes us goal directed and prepared. Meta-cognition is a supreme sense/ awareness to plan, monitor an evaluate our own mental, behaviour an emotional functioning. It works like a regulator of mental abilities. So if we want to become knowledgeable we have to develop the Meta-cognition (observer) of own mental processing. Anthony Magnacca quoted, "Meta-cognition involves choosing the best way to approach a learning task, students with good meta-cognitive skills, set goal, organize their activities, select among various approaches to learning, and change strategies of needed." A lot of research indicated that meta-cognition improve learning, memory thinking, problem solving and other cognitive abilities. Bransford, Brown and Cocking (2000) synthesize a decade of researches at

National Academy of Science, concluded, “the Meta-cognitive approach is the best effective approach to instruction. Meta-cognition practices increase students abilities to transfer or adopt their learning to new context and tasks.” Rachille Dene Poth (2019) stated that “Meta-cognition helps in social emotional learning. Again he says that to promote Meta-cognition we can use - (i) Relationships, (ii) Thinking aloud, (iii) Share ideas, (iv) Use resources and visible thinking. Meta-cognition ability makes us much more sensible and planner so that contribute in the problem solving.

The Meta-cognitive practices develop the wisdom among students. The theory of ‘Triarchic theory of successful intelligence’ explains the higher level of mental processes involve in intelligence and as well as wisdom. Sturnberg believes that there is a universal process of intelligence is found among human beings. Information processing occurs in three stages or it serve three functions:

1. Metacognitive works : Planning and monitoring it called executive process. eg. Analytical intelligence.
2. Performance Component involves in the implementation of the strategies. eg. Creative Intelligence.
3. Knowledge acquisition component involves in the new knowledge gaining responses. eg. Practical intelligence.

The above three component of intelligence involves in the development of ‘Wisdom’. Wisdom is the ability to make sensible decisions and judgement because of your knowledge and experience. Wisdom is the ultimate cognition which use meta-cognitive skills, performance skills and knowledge acquisition skills. It is the centre of the whole cognitive activities. The role of wisdom is to synthesize the meta-cognition performance and learning. It also leads the wholistic approach to regulate and control all activities. The theory of Sternberg explain with the name of Balance theory because wisdom balance among the mental processing. Wisdom also decide the right doing from the wrong doing. So wisdom include the cognitive emotional and behavioural aspects of the individual. So finally it can be stated that ‘Wisdom’ is the ultimate aim of all types of learning. But unfortunately our whole education system is emphasizing to develop the analytical intelligence to collecting a lot of information. Wisdom develops a sense of synthesis the life, not only outside world but also within the individual. It is a matter of interdisciplinary and holistic approach of mental activities and thinking, emotion and behaviour and leads to the all round development of the personality. On the other hand, if we focus on the intelligence only, than we prepare the computer mind without sensibility, emotion and compassion. One another thing must be added that wisdom is the ability /concept which is the matter of psychology as well as philosophy. Philosophy and intellectual tradition of Indian society emphasized on the consciousness and assumed that whole personality and human behaviour govern by consciousness. The concept of ‘Wisdom’ is near to philosophy as well as it connect to the psychology. The concept of wisdom reflect the multi-disciplinary characteristics. Definitely it will be a “Concept of future.”

Thus at last, it can be concluded that to becoming knowledgeable we must promote ‘Wisdom’ in place of intelligence. Wisdom include in itself the concept of intelligence, emotional intelligence, social intelligence and ideal behaviour so that a

simple and holistic approach will be developed that will help the all round development of a human being.

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